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Influence of Social Media on Collaborative Learning among Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the Influence of Social Media on Collaborative Learning among Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt metropolis. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study, the population of the study was 18,298 Senior Secondary School Students from 47 Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt metropolis. Self- designed questionnaire titled Influence of Social Media on collaborative learning (ISMCL) was used. The instrument was given face validation from two experts of Measurement and Evaluation and one expert of Educational Psychology from the Department of Educational Foundations and Educational Psychology, Guidance and counselling respectively. The reliability of the instrument was done using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and coefficient index of 0.70 was obtained. The study was guided by five research questions and five null hypotheses. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer research questions, while independent T-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that Facebook, WhatsApp Instagram, and Tiktok social media platforms had significant influence while X social media platform showed moderate significant difference on public senior secondary school students' collaborative learning. Based on this finding, it was recommended that public Secondary Schools' heads and teachers should engage the use of social media platform for instructional delivery. Schools to develop policy framework guided the usage of social media for collaborative learning among students.

Keywords: Collaborative Learning, Social Media, Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, Tiktok

INTRODUCTION

The outstanding method of equipping learners with knowledge and skill through education is by instructional delivery exercise of teaching and learning. However, the effectiveness of instructional exercise of teaching and learning is a function of the approach adopted by teachers and instructors Chad (2022). Collaborative learning as an umbrella concept used to explain a joint learning activities that attracts individual active participation for the purpose of acquiring knowledge and skills. Closely related to this description is the position of Aritani, et al., (2022) who defined collaborative learning as a new approach and pattern of knowledge impartation that attracts the attainment of learning outcome through active efforts of learners. It is thus an online digital network mechanism of promoting active learning.

Collaborative learning is a practical operative or team work that is poised towards the attainment of stated learning goals. Collaborative learning attracts the adoption of learning by doing based on theory of John Dewey (Amadi 2021). The adoption of this theory underscore the fact that active participation of each member of a collaborative learning approach remains an undisputable resource that has the capacity to encourage, and motivate other members of a group towards active participation. This further suggest that in a secondary school system, operational reality of classroom instructional delivery exercise should as a matter of positive learning outcome, reflect active

participation of all learners. Emphasis on the veracity of these expression underpin the fact that inactive participation of individual member of a group may jeopardise the collective agenda of quality learning outcome of formal teaching and learning exercise.

Social media has become information and communication tool that cuts across all facets of human endeavour especially the educational sector. Social media may have been described in different ways among authors based on their understanding (Nielsen, 2019). Social media as opined by Nielsen (2019) is a creation of online universal interactive approach and platform which acts as a digital necessity for meeting the entertainment and education of daily emerging knowledge seekers. Another interesting idea about the concept of social media is the consideration of Mayhew and Wagle (2019) which described social media as a set of online application of information and communication tool that provides avenue that facilitate social interaction among digital users, create knowledge, share and transfer a monologue into a dialogue. Onisoya and Mbaba, (2024) described social media as technologies, such as blogs, video-sharing platforms (such as YouTube), presentation-sharing platforms (such as SlideShare), social networking platforms (such as Facebook and LinkedIn), instant messaging platforms (such as Skype), and groupware platforms (such as Google Docs). These social media platforms allow users to have conversations, share information and create web content.

Akegu (2022) inferred that in this part of the world (Nigeria) social media is a novelty invention for communication exercise traceable to the emergence of telephone and digital platform for entertainment, education, information dissemination and socialization practices. Mbaba, and Jimoh (2022) opined that the increasing use of social media and mobile technology for coursework has recently been observed among college students. This is because social media by its nature have the capabilities of educating, informing and entertaining its audience.

The operational reality of social media for information dissemination, education entertainment and socialization may take different forms. However, in this study, consideration of the various platforms of social media will center on "Face-book, WhatsApp, Instagram, X and Tik-tok". The fact that education through its teaching and learning exercise remains the most veritable tool that can influence behaviour through its impactful nature attracts the thought that social media and the above identified platform may equally influence individual and group of people especially in a collaborative learning environment (Oberst, 2019). The certainty of such influence which may take either a negative or positive form is a major factor of consideration of this study.

Statement of the Problem

The past two decades have witnessed unprecedented revolution in the field of technological applications specifically in the teaching and learning process. Technology has become an essential component of this process. Facebook and WhatsApp for example have been successfully used in engaging students in collaborative learning within Port Harcourt Metropolis hence teachers are able to reach learners with both face to face contact and online tools. On the other hand, learners are able to access instructions asynchronously. This approach enhances convenience in terms of time, location and flexibility.

However, the researcher observed that the use of social media in collaborative learning poses a serious challenge because it is not clear whether the use of social media as a tool influences student's collaborative learning. Furthermore, it is not clear if the use of face book, Instagrame, X, and others have significant influence on collaborative learning. This research is therefore aimed at investigating the influence of Social Media on collaborative learning among Senior Secondary Schools students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Purpose of the Study

This study is aimed at achieving the following purpose:

1. examine the influence of Facebook on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State.

2. ascertain the influence of WhatsApp on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State.
3. determine the influence of Instagram on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State.
4. find out the influence of X on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State.
5. determine the influence of Tik-Tok on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State.

Research Questions

1. What is the influence of Facebook platform on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School students of Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State?
2. What is the influence of WhatsApp on collaborative learning amongst public senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State?
3. What is the influence of Instagram on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State?
4. What is the influence of X on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State?
5. What is the influence of Tik-Tok on collaborative learning amongst Public Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the influence of Facebook on collaborative learning between male and female students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference in the influence of WhatsApp on collaborative learning between male and female students in public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Rivers State.
3. There is no significant difference in the influence of Instagram on collaborative learning between male and female students in Public Senior Secondary School in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Rivers State.
4. There is no significant difference in the influence of X on collaborative learning between male and female students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Rivers State.
5. There is no significant difference in the influence of Tik-Tok on collaborative learning between male and female students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Metropolis. Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey design, with a population of 18298 students from 47 senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis. Taro-Yamen's formula was used to determine the sample size of 392 students used for the study. Random sampling technique was adopted to select 25 public senior secondary schools which represents about 50% of the schools in Port Harcourt metropolis. In each of the 25 selected public senior secondary schools, the accidental sampling technique was adopted to select 16 SSS III senior secondary school students in each of the schools. Purposive sampling was used to sample 392 finally used in this study.

Self –design questionnaire title Influence of Social Media on Collaborative learning (ISMCL), the questionnaire adopt 4point Likert scale, with option such as Strongly Agree (SA) – 4 points, Agree (A) – 3 points, Disagree (D) – 2 points, Strongly Disagree (SD) – 1 point. The instrument was face validation by three experts; one of Psychology Guidance and Counselling and two from Measurement and Evaluation from Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. The reliability of the instrument was tested

using 20 students and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Was used to obtain 0.70 coefficient index, the instrument was deemed reliable for use. The instruments were administered and total of 380 questionnaire were retrieved and used for the study. Data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions, while t- test was adopted to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DICUSSION

Research Question 1: What is the influence of Facebook platform on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School students of Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State?

Table 1: Summary of mean and standard deviation on the influence of Facebook platform on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School students of Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.	Decision
1	The adoption of Facebook motivates my participation in group instructional delivery exercise.	106	176	89	9	3.00	0.78	Agreed
2	The adoption of Facebook encourages my participation in group instructional delivery exercise.	139	121	108	12	3.02	0.88	Agreed
3	The adoption of Facebook helps my learning ability from other students during instructional delivery exercise.	215	89	54	22	3.31	0.92	Agreed
4	The adoption of Facebook platform in group learning promote my concentration during instructional delivery exercise.	96	150	67	67	2.72	1.03	Agreed
5	The adoption of Facebook platform boost my interactive capacity in the midst of students.	121	76	129	54	2.69	1.07	Agreed
Grand mean						2.95	0.60	Agreed

The result from Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation on the influence of Facebook platform on collaborative learning. The grand mean on the influence of Facebook was found to be 2.95 ± 0.60 . The result further shows that respondents agreed that the adoption of Facebook helps their learning ability from other students during instructional delivery exercise, with a mean of 3.31 ± 0.92 , the result indicates that adoption of Facebook platform boosts interactive capacity in the midst of students had the least mean of 2.69 ± 1.07 .

Research Question 2: What is the influence of WhatsApp on collaborative learning amongst public senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State?

Table 2: Summary of mean and standard deviation on the influence of WhatsApp on collaborative learning amongst public senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.	Decision
6	The adoption of WhatsApp promotes my interest to learn from other students.	90	146	81	63	2.69	1.01	Agreed

7	The adoption of WhatsApp facilitates my participation among students during instructional delivery exercise.	121	124	91	44	2.85	1.00	Agreed
8	Reading other students' ideas through WhatsApp platform stimulates my learning ability.	182	71	91	36	3.05	1.05	Agreed
9	The adoption of WhatsApp platform in learning has a positive influence in my group assignment.	138	125	50	67	2.88	1.09	Agreed
10	The adoption of WhatsApp platform promotes free interaction during instructional delivery exercise.	175	109	87	9	3.18	0.87	Agreed
Grand mean						2.93	0.56	Agreed

The result from Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation on the influence of WhatsApp on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School students. The grand mean on the influence of WhatsApp was 2.93 ± 0.56 . This proved that WhatsApp platform influences collaborative learning among public senior secondary school students.

Research Question 3: What is the influence of Instagram on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State?

Table 3: Summary of mean and standard deviation on the influence of Instagram on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.	Decision
1	The use of Instagram social media motivates my learning efforts in the midst of other students.	219	96	45	20	3.35	0.88	Agreed
2	Using Instagram social media facilitates learning from other students	223	72	42	43	3.25	1.04	Agreed
3	The adoption of social media facilitates my participation during instructional delivery exercise.	194	126	20	40	3.25	0.96	Agreed
4	The adoption of Instagram social media promotes free interaction during instruction delivery exercise.	244	82	25	29	3.42	0.91	Agreed
5	The adoption of Instagram social media has a negative influence on my learning ability among other students.	196	124	52	8	3.34	0.79	Agreed
Grand mean						3.32	0.41	Agreed

The result from Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation on the influence of Instagram on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt metropolis. The grand mean 3.32 ± 0.41 among other results as analysed. The overall result shows that Instagram influence collaborative learning in schools.

Research Question 4: What is the influence of X on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State?

Table 4: Summary of mean and standard deviation on the influence of X on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.	Decision
1	The adoption of X social media platform in teaching promotes effective interaction among students.	116	91	107	66	2.68	1.09	Agreed
2	The adoption of X social media platform in teaching motivates my learning efforts.	119	128	54	79	2.76	1.11	Agreed
3	Listening and reading other students' contribution through the X social media encourages my effort of contributing in group learning.	113	104	49	114	2.57	1.20	Agreed
4	The adoption of X social media platform in teaching has positive influence to my learning outcome.	111	125	32	112	2.62	1.19	Agreed
5	The adoption of X social media platform promotes my participatory effort during learning.	113	153	37	77	2.79	1.08	Agreed
Grand mean						2.68	0.68	Agreed

The result from Table 4 shows the mean and standard deviation on the influence of X on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt metropolis. The grand mean on the influence of X was found to be 2.68 ± 0.68 . The overall findings indicates that X influence students' collaborative learning in public schools.

Research Question 5: What is the influence of Tik-Tok on collaborative learning amongst Public Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State?

Table 5: Summary of mean and standard deviation on the influence of Tik-Tok on collaborative learning amongst Public Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt metropolis in Rivers State.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.	Decision
1	The adoption of Tik-Tok social media platform motivates my learning effort.	143	124	66	47	2.96	1.02	Agreed
2	The adoption of Tik-Tok social media platform has positive influence to my personal effort to learning.	129	125	78	48	2.88	1.02	Agreed
3	The adoption of Tik-Tok social media platform in teaching promotes my participatory effort in learning.	116	135	70	59	2.81	1.04	Agreed
4	Reading and listening other students' contributions on Tik-Tok social media platform promotes my commitment to learning.	120	130	33	97	2.72	1.16	Agreed
5	Reading and listening to other students' contribution through Tik-Tok platform quickens my thinking faculty.	137	108	64	71	2.82	1.12	Agreed
Grand mean						2.84	0.57	Agreed

The result from Table 5 shows the mean and standard deviation on the influence of Tik-Tok on collaborative learning amongst public Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt metropolis. The grand mean on the influence of Tik-Tok was found to be 2.84 ± 0.57 . Based on the foregoing, the answer to research question five is that Tik-Tok platform influences collaborative learning among public senior secondary school students.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the influence of Facebook on collaborative learning between male and female students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Table 6: Summary of independent sample t-test on the difference in the influence of Facebook on collaborative learning between male and female students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	SEM	t-cal	df	t-crit	Decision
Male	173	3.05	0.71	0.05				
					0.003	378	1.962	Retained
Female	207	2.87	0.46	0.03				

The result from Table 6 shows the summary of the independent sample t-test on the difference in the influence of Facebook on collaborative learning between male and female students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The calculated t-value was 0.003, with a degree of freedom of 378 and a t-critical value of 1.962. This result indicates that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female students on the influence of Facebook on collaborative learning. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained at 0.05 level of significance. This result indicates that there is no significant difference in the influence of facebook between male and female.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the influence of WhatsApp on collaborative learning between male and female students in public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Table 7: Summary of independent sample t-test on the difference in the influence of WhatsApp on collaborative learning between male and female students in public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	SEM	t-cal	df	t-crit	Decision
Male	173	2.99	0.62	0.05				
					0.047	378	1.962	Retained
Female	207	2.88	0.51	0.04				

The result from Table 7 shows the summary of the independent sample t-test on the difference in the influence of WhatsApp on collaborative learning between male and female students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The calculated t-value was 0.047, with a degree of freedom of 378 and a t-critical value of 1.962. This result indicates that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female students on the influence of WhatsApp on collaborative learning. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained at 0.05 level of significance. The hypothesis is retained because there is no significant influence of WhatssApp platform on collaborative learning between male and female students in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the influence of Instagram on collaborative learning between male and female students in Public Senior Secondary School in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	SEM	t-cal	df	t-crit	Decision
Male	173	3.31	0.45	0.03	0.666	378	1.962	Retained
Female	207	3.33	0.37	0.03				

The result from Table 8 shows the summary of the independent sample t-test on the difference in the influence of Instagram on collaborative learning between male and female students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The calculated t-value was 0.666, with a degree of freedom of 378 and a t-critical value of 1.962. This result indicates that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female students on the influence of Instagram on collaborative learning. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained at the 0.05 level of significance. This implies that

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the influence of X on collaborative learning between male and female students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	SEM	t-cal	df	t-crit	Decision
Male	173	2.71	0.68	0.05	0.439	378	1.962	Retained
Female	207	2.66	0.67	0.05				

The result from Table 9 shows the summary of the independent sample t-test on the difference in the influence of X on collaborative learning between male and female students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The calculated t-value was 0.439, with a degree of freedom of 378 and a t-critical value of 1.962. This result indicates that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female students on the influence of X on collaborative learning. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Hypothesis 4) is retained at the 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant difference in the influence of Tik-Tok on collaborative learning between male and female students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Metropolis, Rivers State.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	SEM	t-cal	df	t-crit	Decision
Male	173	2.84	0.58	0.04	0.824	378	1.962	Retained
Female	207	2.83	0.56	0.04				

The result from Table 10 shows the summary of the independent sample t-test on the difference in the influence of Tik-Tok on collaborative learning between male and female students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The calculated t-value was 0.824, with a degree of freedom of 378 and a t-critical value of 1.962. This result indicates that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female students on the influence of Tik-Tok on collaborative learning. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Hypothesis 5) is retained at the 0.05 level of significance.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of this present study which indicates that Facebook moderately influences collaborative learning of students with the highest agreement in its ability to aid peer learning is in tandem with the position of Young (2021) who described that Facebook has an operational focus of connectivity of friends, relationships, sharing of ideas and accommodation of various contribution of user across the entire globe. This study equally agree with the findings several research that underscores the need to overcome inferiority complex among students in their interactions through Facebook as it improve students' ability to express themselves during classroom interactive exercise (Duncan & Brezyk, 2020; Afrose, 2024).

The finding of this study showed strong positive influence on collaborative learning especially in promoting free interaction and motivation of learners. This is in alliance with the study of Jaal and Nawab (2020) who maintained that Instagram social media platform remains an interest motivation outfit that stimulates individual participatory exercise among learners Instagram social media platform has a functional collaborative advantage that promotes knowledge impactful exercise from the teachers and productive learning outcome among learners.

The finding of this study which indicated that WhatsApp platform promotes interactive and group learning especially through free interaction and reading students ideas is in agreement with the Udenze and Oshionebo (2020) who recognized that the adoption of WhatsApp social media as a benefit of technological advancement has become an undisputable trend in educational institutions especially in the area of instructional delivery exercise. The finding of this study is equally intone with Aicha (2020) who maintained that WhatsApp social media platform is a resourceful channel of great benefits to students collaborative learning, noting that WhatsApp platform provides students with online advantage of exchanging messages, images, videos, voice notes. It equally facilitates teachers or instructors ability to create and address different groups of students via a platform that can save cost, prevent risk associated with air, sea and land journey for the purpose of achieving physical learning outcome.

The finding of this present study which showed strong positive influence on collaborative learning especially in promoting free interaction and motivation of learners is in alliance with these posture of Jaal and Nawab (2020) who maintained that Instagram social media platform remains an interest motivation outfit that stimulates individual participatory exercise among group of persons. The finding of this study further proved the expression of Zivojinovic et al, (2025) as a useful literature to knowledge expansion. This is to the extent that Instagram social media platform and its operational reality is designed to display and share photos, videos, art work, images which inturn promotes image foundation, stimulation of ideas and mimicking of interesting expressions, styles and ideas of other users across the globe via online media platform.

The finding of this study which indicated relatively low influence on collaborative learning is at variance with the logic of Moneme (2020) which pinpointed that effective utilization of x social media platform constitutes in empowerment outfit for teachers to the attainment of expansionary benefit of impactful exercise to students through an equipped online instructional capacity index. Though it may be a resourceful outfit that equips teachers with contemporary and functional instruction content, functional instructional delivery method geared towards productive learning outcome among learners as adduced by Moneme (2020), however, the findings of this study indicates that its operational outfit may not possess positive and productive channel for collaborative learning among learners.

The finding of this study which sowed a moderate influence on students' collaborative learning is in tandem with the finding of Uhasawneh et al, (2024) whose research exercise on the exploration of language learning platform on Tik-Tok and Instagram towards collaborative learning outcome of foreign language of undergraduates proved that effective utilization of Tik-tok social media platform is a functional channel of collaborative learning process that promotes students overall language learning outcome. The finding of the study equally supports the position of Daniel, et al (2021). This is because its finding on the influence of social media platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, X, Tik-Tok which indicated high level of creativity impart through collaborative

practices of technological advancement tends to be devalued based on the finding of the present study. The implication of this finding which indicates the rejection of its null hypothesis proves an output of variance to the finding of this present study.

The findings from the reviewed literature pinpointed considerable level of negative emotional and interactive influence of Tik-Tok with detrimental effect to students' concentration, commitment to study and productive learning outcome. This study is closely related to the present one based on their similarity of focus towards the influence of Tik-Tok social media to students' learning outcome.

CONCLUSION

The finding of this study which focused on the influence of social media to collaborative learning shows as thus: Facebook moderately influences collaborative learning among students, with the highest agreement on its ability to aid peer learning (M = 3.31). There was no significant difference between male and female students in their responses, thus the null hypothesis was retained. WhatsApp was found to promote interactive and group learning, especially through free interaction and reading peers' ideas (M = 3.18 and 3.05 respectively). No significant gender difference was observed, so the null hypothesis was upheld. Instagram showed a strong positive influence on collaborative learning, especially in promoting free interaction and motivation to learn (M = 3.42 and 3.35 respectively). The t-test indicated no significant gender difference, and the null hypothesis was retained. The use of X showed a relatively low influence on collaborative learning, with the highest mean related to promoting participatory effort (M = 2.79). Gender did not significantly influence responses, so the null hypothesis was accepted. The bottom line of this finding is that social is indeed good for collaborative learning.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the finding of this study and its conclusions, the following recommendations are made:

1. Public Secondary Schools' heads and teachers should engage social media platform such as Facebook, Intagrame, WhatsApp and others for instructional delivery in schools.
2. Schools should develop policy framework to guide the use of social media in lesson delivery and teachers should adhere to precautionary usage of social media in collaborative learning.
3. Institution of learning and teachers should have the liberty to choose what media is appropriate for their learners.
4. Institution and parents should be encouraged to procure smart phones for collaborative learning in school.
5. Institution of learning, should organized seminars for students and teachers on the effectiveness of social media in learning and the challenges around its usage.

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